

Reasoning Large Language Models for Clinical Coding

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Abstract

Accurate ICD-10 classification of clinical narratives is essential for billing, research, and healthcare planning but remains a labor intensive and error prone task. This study evaluates the effectiveness of LLMs, particularly those equipped with reasoning capabilities, in automating ICD-10 code assignment from discharge summaries. Using 1,500 annotated summaries from the MIMIC-IV database across 10 ICD-10 codes, we compared eleven LLMs, five reasoning and six non-reasoning, under a consistent zero-shot prompting strategy. Performance was assessed using F1 scores across different diagnosis types (primary vs. all) and ICD-10 code granularities (Level 3 to Level 5). Results showed that reasoning models such as DeepSeek Reasoner and Gemini 2.5 Pro significantly outperformed their counterparts, especially at broader classification levels. Our findings suggest that reasoning augmented LLMs offer substantial promise for enhancing the accuracy and efficiency of clinical code assignment and merit further exploration in healthcare NLP applications.

Keywords

Reasoning, Large Language Model, ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Clinical Coding, Gemini, Llama, Qwen

1. Introduction

Accurate and efficient assignment of the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-10) codes to clinical narratives such as discharge summaries is a critical task in healthcare systems, supporting billing, epidemiological research, and healthcare planning [1]. Traditionally, this process is performed manually by trained clinical coders, which can be time consuming, error prone, and costly. With the increasing availability of electronic health records and advancements in natural language processing (NLP), there is growing interest in automating medical coding using machine learning and, more recently, large language models (LLMs) [2].

While LLMs such as GPT-4, Gemini, and LLaMA have demonstrated remarkable performance on general NLP benchmarks [3], their effectiveness in specialized clinical tasks like ICD-10 classification remains underexplored. Moreover, the reasoning capabilities of certain models are often cited as a potential advantage in complex classification tasks [4]. In this study, we present a comparative evaluation of eleven different LLMs, some designed with explicit reasoning abilities and others not, on the task of ICD-10 code classification using discharge summaries from the Medical Information Mart for Intensive Care dataset (MIMIC-IV). We evaluate the accuracy of each model by comparing the predicted ICD-10 codes to ground truth annotations and report performance using F1 scores.

2. Related Work

Mustafa et al. [5] conducted a study comparing various reasoning and non-reasoning LLMs for the classification of clinical discharge summaries. They selected 3,000 discharge summaries, both positive and negative, corresponding to 10 distinct ICD-10 codes from the MIMIC-IV database. The LLMs were

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tasked with determining whether each summary corresponded to a specific ICD-10 code. To assess consistency, each model processed the same discharge summaries across three separate trials. The findings indicated that reasoning based models demonstrated superior accuracy, with Gemini 2 Flash Thinking achieving the highest F1 score of 75.50%. In terms of consistency, GPT-3o Mini emerged as the most reliable model, with a consistency rate of 95.47%.

Soroush et al. [6] benchmarked the performance of LLMs, GPT-3.5, GPT-4, Gemini Pro, and LLaMa2-70b Chat, in generating ICD-9-CM, ICD-10-CM, and CPT codes when given code descriptions. Using MIMIC-IV, researchers evaluated LLMs' ability to match code descriptions with their correct codes. GPT-4 showed the best performance but still had low exact match rates (33.9%–49.8%), while others performed worse, with LLaMa2-70b Chat performing the poorest. Even when incorrect, some models provided equivalent and generalized codes, but fabricated and nonbillable codes were common. The study concludes that current LLMs are unreliable for medical code querying tasks without further development, as they often generate imprecise or invalid outputs.

3. The Problem

In recent years, dozens of LLMs have been developed with the ability to process and analyze clinical documents. Some of these models incorporate reasoning capabilities designed to enhance their performance in complex tasks such as medical coding [2, 7]. This raises critical questions: Can LLMs match or even exceed the performance of human clinical coders? Could they act as intelligent assistants to support human coders rather than replace them outright? Most importantly, which LLMs offer the best performance in the specific task of ICD-10 classification from clinical narratives?

4. Framework

4.1. Clinical Documents

Clinical coding is a vital process in healthcare systems that involves translating medical diagnoses, procedures, and services into standardized codes, such as those found in ICD-10 codes. These codes are essential for billing, statistical analysis, and clinical research [8]. Traditionally, clinical coding has been a manual task performed by trained human coders. However, with the rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly LLMs, new possibilities have emerged for automating this process. While current LLMs are not yet capable of completely replacing human coders [9], they have shown the potential to significantly enhance coding speed and reduce operational costs by minimizing the need for large teams of human coders [10].

4.2. LLMs

For this study, we selected 11 LLMs to evaluate their performance in ICD-10 code classification. Five of these models are designed with explicit reasoning capabilities: DeepSeek Reasoner, Gemini 2.0 Flash Thinking, Gemini 2.5 Pro, GPT-03 Mini, and Qwen QWQ. These models represent the most advanced reasoning-enabled LLMs available at the time of writing.

To contrast the performance of reasoning models, we also selected six LLMs that do not feature built-in reasoning mechanisms: DeepSeek Chat, Gemini 2.0 Flash, GPT-4o, GPT-4o Mini, LLaMA 3.3, and LLaMA 4 Scout. None of the models were fine-tuned for this task. Instead, we used a zero-shot approach, submitting queries directly to each model via their respective APIs. To streamline the experimentation process, we developed a custom Visual Studio desktop application to interface with the APIs and manage input/output operations. This application, along with its documentation, is available via GitHub: <https://github.com/asmgx/LLMs>.

4.3. Dataset

The dataset used for this experiment consisted of 1,500 discharge summaries obtained from the publicly available MIMIC-IV clinical database. We focused on ten commonly used ICD-10 codes that are frequently encountered in hospital settings. For each selected ICD-10 code, we randomly sampled 150 discharge summaries that were annotated with that code in the original dataset. Since each summary could include multiple ICD-10 codes, the classification task was inherently multi-label in nature. The gold standard for evaluation was the set of ICD-10 codes originally assigned in MIMIC-IV.

To ensure consistency and readability for LLMs, we implemented a preprocessing pipeline using the Clinical Text Analysis and Knowledge Extraction System (cTAKES). This pipeline was applied to each summary to extract relevant clinical entities, remove non-informative content, normalize medical terminologies, and eliminate formatting artifacts. As a result, the cleaned summaries retained all essential medical information while becoming more suitable for analysis by language models [11].

4.4. Evaluation Metrics

We employed the F1 score as the primary evaluation metric due to its effectiveness in balancing precision and recall in multi-label classification settings [Mustafa and Rahimi Azghadi, 2024]. The F1 score enables us to quantify not only the accuracy of the predicted codes but also how comprehensively the model captures all relevant codes. Calculating F1 scores required defining true positives, false positives, and false negatives. The F1 score is calculated as shown in Equation (1):

$$F_1 = \frac{2 \cdot TP}{2 \cdot TP + FP + FN}. \quad (1)$$

To thoroughly evaluate model performance, we assessed F1 scores across six different settings. These included two clinical contexts, All Diagnoses (both primary and secondary diagnoses) and Primary Diagnoses only, crossed with three levels of ICD-10 granularity: Level 5 (most specific, e.g., I25.42), Level 4 (e.g., I25.4), and Level 3 (more general category, e.g., I25). This structure enabled a comprehensive evaluation of each model’s ability to assign both highly specific and general diagnostic codes.

5. Data Analysis

Each of the 1,500 discharge summaries was processed by all 11 LLMs, resulting in a total of 16,500 experiments. Each record was prompted to the LLMs using the following prompt: *"In the role of Clinical Coder, analyze the following medical reports and answer the questions in the specified format [RepText] Provide the answers directly as simple as possible and in this format: #Primary# Then the answer for the first question: What is the primary ICD10 Code diagnoses in format of ###.### ? #Secondary# Then the answer for the second question: What are the secondary ICD10 Code diagnoses in format of ###.### ?"*

In general, none of the evaluated LLMs achieved high accuracy, particularly in the classification of primary diagnoses at Level 5. The highest F1 score in this setting was 7%, achieved by Gemini 2.5. However, performance improved as the classification task became less granular. For example, DeepSeek Chat achieved an F1 score of 12% at Level 5 for all diagnoses, which increased to 28% at Level 3. This trend indicates that LLMs perform better when assigning broader diagnostic categories, as reduced label granularity simplifies the classification task.

The performance disparity between primary diagnoses and all diagnoses was also notable. For instance, GPT-4o achieved F1 scores of 10%, 13%, and 22% across Levels 5 to 3, respectively, when evaluating all diagnoses. In contrast, its F1 scores for primary diagnoses were significantly lower: 3%, 8%, and 9%. As illustrated in Figure 1, this difference is due to the binary nature of primary diagnosis classification, where only a single label is correct, allowing less room for partial matches compared to the multi-label classification used for all diagnoses.

Overall, models with reasoning capabilities consistently outperformed non-reasoning models, as shown in Figure 1. The DeepSeek Reasoner and Gemini 2.5 Pro demonstrated the highest F1 scores.

Figure 1: Average of F1 Score by Metric and Model Type.

Average of F1 Score by Metric and Model Type

Model Type ● Non-Reasoning ● Reasoning

Table 1

F1 Scores of LLMs Across Different ICD-10 Granularity Levels and Diagnosis Types

Model	Level 5 Primary	Level 5 All	Level 4 Primary	Level 4 All	Level 3 Primary	Level 3 All
Deepseek Reasoner	4.51%	16.66%	10.09%	20.00%	13.28%	31.43%
Gemini 2.0 Flash Thinking	1.06%	4.32%	7.92%	8.27%	9.50%	13.84%
Gemini 2.5 Pro	7.48%	23.67%	12.96%	27.41%	16.30%	39.12%
GPT o3 Mini	4.39%	7.64%	10.91%	12.20%	12.38%	21.28%
Qwen QWQ	0.69%	3.78%	4.92%	10.03%	10.04%	22.36%
Deepseek Chat	1.52%	11.90%	3.32%	15.60%	11.60%	28.17%
Gemini 2.0 Flash	2.05%	7.03%	5.77%	9.56%	6.46%	17.38%
GPT 4o	2.78%	10.20%	7.55%	12.74%	8.75%	21.52%
GPT 4o Mini	2.91%	10.71%	6.92%	13.24%	8.65%	24.42%
Llama 3.3	2.38%	8.34%	5.41%	10.33%	8.80%	20.80%
Llama 4 Scout	0.11%	4.53%	0.58%	6.49%	4.58%	17.26%

DeepSeek Reasoner achieved 31% for all diagnoses at Level 3 and 13% for primary diagnoses, while Gemini 2.5 Pro slightly surpassed it in broader classification scenarios, reaching 39% for all diagnoses at Level 3 and 16% for primary diagnoses. In contrast, the best performing non-reasoning models, such as GPT 4o Mini and DeepSeek Chat, achieved lower scores 24% and 9% for GPT 4o Mini, and 28% and 12% for DeepSeek Chat under the same evaluation conditions. A complete breakdown of performance across models is provided in Table 1.

The consistent gap in F1 scores between reasoning and non-reasoning models suggests a meaningful performance differential. The repeated top ranking of reasoning models such as DeepSeek Reasoner and Gemini 2.5 Pro supports the hypothesis that integrating reasoning capabilities enhances performance in multi-label classification of clinical texts. These findings underscore the potential value of reasoning augmented LLMs for complex tasks such as ICD-10 code assignment from discharge summaries.

6. Discussion

The results show that, on average, reasoning LLMs perform better in ICD-10 code classification from discharge summaries, primarily due to one high-performing model (Gemini 2.5 Pro), while the others perform comparably to non-reasoning models (see Table 1). Models such as DeepSeek Reasoner and Gemini 2.5 Pro consistently outperformed their non-reasoning counterparts across all granularity levels and diagnosis types. This suggests that reasoning capabilities may allow models to better interpret complex clinical narratives, particularly when associating symptoms, procedures, and test results with the appropriate codes. Additionally, the observed trend of improved performance at broader ICD-10 levels indicates that while detailed classification remains challenging, models are increasingly reliable at higher level categorization. This is particularly relevant in real world clinical applications, where accurate general classification can still offer significant value.

Despite these promising results, several limitations must be acknowledged. The dataset consisted of 1,500 discharge summaries focused on only 10 ICD-10 codes, which may introduce selection bias and limit generalizability. Furthermore, while reasoning models showed superior performance, their advantage was most notable at higher levels of abstraction, with limited gains at the most detailed coding level. This suggests that both reasoning and non-reasoning models may benefit from domain specific fine-tuning or ensemble methods that combine strengths of multiple models. Future work should explore larger and more diverse code sets, apply few-shot or in-context learning strategies tailored to the clinical domain, and investigate hybrid pipelines that integrate rule based systems with LLMs for improved granularity and reliability in ICD-10 classification.

7. Conclusion

This study provides evidence that LLMs equipped with reasoning capabilities perform more effectively in automated ICD-10 classification tasks compared to standard LLMs. Reasoning models such as DeepSeek Reasoner and Gemini 2.5 Pro consistently achieved higher F1 scores across varying levels of ICD-10 code granularity and diagnosis types. Their superior performance, especially at broader classification levels, highlights their potential to understand complex clinical narratives and infer relevant diagnostic codes with greater accuracy. Furthermore, the trend of increasing model performance with less granular code levels suggests that while detailed coding remains a challenge, reasoning models can serve as valuable tools for higher level clinical classification.

The implications of these findings are significant for the advancement of clinical coding automation. By leveraging the strengths of reasoning LLMs, healthcare systems can potentially enhance the efficiency and consistency of medical coding processes, reducing manual workload and minimizing errors. For researchers and practitioners working in clinical NLP, these results underscore the importance of selecting models that incorporate reasoning strategies. Future efforts should focus on expanding training datasets, incorporating fine-tuning for medical domains, and exploring ensemble methods to improve performance at the most detailed ICD-10 levels, thereby moving closer to fully automated, reliable coding solutions.

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